

Study on the Effect of Supracricoid Patial Laryngectomy on Swallowing Function and the Effectiveness of Rehabilitation Treatment

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Abstract—Objective: To investigate the effect of supracricoid patial laryngectomy on swallowing function and the effectiveness of rehabilitation treatment. Method: Fifty patients after supracricoid patial laryngectomy and dysphagia received swallowing study with two methods (VESS and VFSS) and swallowing rehabilitation treatment. Result: The two evaluation methods have strong consistency and Swallowing rehabilitation training was effective. Conclusion: VESS is a safe and reliable means to evaluate swallowing function, especially for patients after SCPL. Early postoperative swallowing function training is useful.

Keywords—supracricoid patial laryngectomy; Swallowing function test; rehabilitation

I. INTRODUCTION

The supracricoid patial laryngectomy is a type of functional preservative laryngectomy. It can completely remove the malignant tumors of the larynx while retaining the vocalization, breathing and swallowing functions of the larynx to avoid permanent tracheostomy. This procedure affects the patient's swallowing function [1]. There are currently a variety of methods to assess swallowing function: Fibre Endoscopy Swallowing Function Assessment (FEES); videofluoroscopic swallowing study (VFSS) which is the gold standard and is highly used. FEES is relatively infrequently used. This study evaluated the swallowing function and rehabilitated the patients with laryngeal carcinoma after supracricoid patial laryngectomy, and achieved good results. The reports are as follows:

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Participants

50 patients with laryngocarcinoma who had come to our department from January 2016 to January 2018 after supracricoid patial laryngectomy who visited our department for "dysphagia", including 43 men and 7 women, with an average age of 63.35. At the age of 56-73 years, all patients were diagnosed with laryngocarcinoma who underwent supracricoid patial laryngectomy. There were 41 patients with gastric tube, and 9 patients who can oral feed but felt difficulty in eating.

B. Methods

Endoscopy and videofluoroscopic swallowing study were used to evaluate the swallowing function of all patients. The two examinations must be completed within two days. In order to avoid subjective judgment errors, the two sets of inspections are performed by two different inspectors. Videofluoroscopic swallowing study: the patient swallowed 1, 3, and 5 ml of iohexol-containing food of different traits (water, thin paste, thick paste, semi-solid) in sequence, if there is a large amount of aspiration, stop the inspection. An experienced radiologist and two evaluators who have been specially trained in the diagnosis and treatment of dysphagia repeatedly review the examination video and discuss with them to reach an agreement to evaluate the stages of swallowing and the degree of aspiration.

Endoscopic swallowing function test: the patient contracted the nasal cavity and was superficially anesthetized (nasal cavity only). The electronic laryngoscope was inserted into the oropharynx through one side of the nasal cavity. The anatomical structure of the pharyngeal cavity and larynx cavity (after surgery) and also the secretion was observed first; then the patient swallow 1, 3, and 5 ml of foods of different traits (water, thin paste, thick paste, semi-solid) stained with apple green food pigment in sequence, and stop the inspection when a large number of accidental aspiration occur. Two experienced otolaryngology doctors, who have been specially trained in the diagnosis and treatment of dysphagia, observed on site and repeatedly reviewed the examination videos, and discussed and reached an agreement to evaluate each stage of swallowing and the degree of aspiration.

Evaluation criterion: The pooling, residue, penetration and aspiration of each patient were counted. Pooling: accumulation of food in the vallecula epiglottica or pyriform fossa before swallowing. Residue: the condition in which food remains in the vallecula epiglottica or pyriform fossa after swallowing. Penetration: the condition in which food enters the vestibule of the larynx. Aspiration: the condition in which food or liquid enters the airway or lung through the vestibule of the larynx.

Rehabilitation: After a comprehensive swallowing evaluation of the included patients, a targeted training program is developed. On the 7th day after surgery, rehabilitation training for swallowing function was carried out. Mainly include the following methods: ① cold stimulation of the pharyngeal then swallow, and then instruct the patient to repeat the empty swallowing action, 10 to 15 seconds each time, 3 times a day. ②

Breath-holding and voice exercise: let the patient sit on the chair, hold the chair surface with both hands to hold the breath for pushing exercise, and then suddenly release the hand, the glottis wide open, and exhale, each time 5 ~ 10min, 3 ~ 4 times a day. ③Masako exercise: extend the tongue forward, lightly bite the front of the tongue, and swallow at the same time, 5 to 10 minutes each time, 3 to 4 times a day. ④ Head and neck movement: the head rotates, leans forward, and leans, etc., every 10 to 15 minutes, 3 to 4 times a day. ⑤Mendelsohn action: Instruct the patient to keep the larynx lifted during the swallowing action for 2 ~ 3s, then relax, and repeat the above actions, 5 ~ 10min each time, 3 times a day. ⑥ Oral sensory stimulation training: use a spoon to repeatedly touch the patient's mouth before each meal, use a small amount of acid, spicy, and bitter liquid to stimulate the patient's taste, use cotton sticks or tongue depressor to stimulate the patient's pharyngeal wall, soft palate, tongue base, Every 5 to 10 minutes, 3 to 5 times a day. ⑦Imagination training: After each swallowing training, let the patient imagine the most delicious food they want to eat, and imagine that they are tasting the food, feel the movement of the mouth and tongue during the eating process, if the saliva secretion increases, instruct the patient to swallow. ⑧ Feeding training: After the swallowing function is evaluated, it is possible to safely eat some kind of the food, choose a quiet eating environment, use appropriate traits and a bite of food, eat with a small mouthful fod everytime.All patients underwent re-evaluation of swallowing function after 1 month of rehabilitation.

III. RESULTS

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 23.0 statistical software. Chi-square test tested the consistency of the two inspection methods. And evaluate the changes of swallowing function before and after treatment, and evaluate the treatment effect.

TABLE I. RESULTS OF TWO ASSESSMENT METHODS

	Endoscopy	radiography	Endoscopy	radiography
	thick paste	thick paste	water like	water like
Pooling	27	30	43	44
Residue	46	37	40	44
Penetration	6	4	23	12
Aspiration	7	3	12	20

TABLE II. RESULTS OF TWO ASSESSMENT METHODS AFTER REHABILITATION TREATMENT (N)

	Endoscopy	radiography	Endoscopy	radiography
	thick paste	thick paste	water like	water like
Pooling	18	16	23	25
Residue	22	14	20	24
Penetration	4	2	13	10
Aspiration	3	3	4	5

1. The chi-square test of the two evaluation methods shows that the two evaluation methods have strong consistency, and the Pearson chi-square value is 2.246, indicating that the detection results of the VESS is in good agreement with the evaluation of VFSS

2. The evaluation results after treatment showed that the total effective rate was reached 84%, among which cured cases accounted for 42, ineffective cases were 8, accounted for 16%, 36 patients removed the nasal feeding tube after rehabilitation treatment, 6 patients were able to take part of the food by mouth, and 8 patients had Insufficient intake that couldn't remove the tube.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Laryngeal cancer is the most common tumor in the upper respiratory and digestive tract [2]. The main treatments are surgery (including partial laryngectomy and total laryngectomy) and radiotherapy [3,4]. Depending on the degree of tumor invasion, different levels of laryngectomy (including suprachondral laryngectomy and supraglottic laryngectomy) and reconstruction methods can be used. Supracricoid patial laryngectomy can retain the vocalization, breathing and swallowing functions of the larynx. There are different reports in the literature on the time of gastric tube removal after oral surgery [5-7].

The normal swallowing process includes conscious food intake, food preparation, reflective swallowing food, and esophageal food delivery. The pattern and rhythm of the swallowing process are controlled by the medulla oblongata. Swallowing disorders are symptoms of delay in the process of solid or liquid food from the mouth to the stomach. Aspiration is a common phenomenon of dysphagia, which refers to the food into the trachea accidentally. Long-term aspiration can cause serious complications such as malnutrition, weight loss, and aspiration pneumonia. There are currently a variety of methods to assess laryngeal function (including swallowing function): Fibre Endoscopy Swallowing Function Assessment (FEES); videofluoroscopic swallowing study (VFSS): time of gastric tube removal; whether the protective function of the airway is damaged (such as aspiration) Pneumonia or weight loss) to assess swallowing function; the Quality of Life Questionnaire (QoL) can only give our patients a hint of the subjective sensation of swallowing [8-9].

Patients with laryngeal cancer may have dysphagia before surgery [10]. SCPL changes the anatomical structure of the larynx, destroys the protective physiological function of the larynx, affects the swallowing function of the patient, and is prone to aspiration after surgery, which affects the rehabilitation and quality of life after surgery. The postoperative aspiration rate of SCPL can reach 32%-89%, of which the concealed aspiration is 26.7%, and the incidence of aspiration pneumonia is 4.3%-23% [11].

In terms of swallowing function evaluation, videofluoroscopic swallowing study is recognized as the "gold standard" for swallowing function evaluation. It can conduct detailed evaluation and analysis of the entire swallowing process, and evaluate the status of different stages of swallowing by observing the PA view and Lateral view. During the

examination, the patient can be instructed to complete the swallowing using appropriate eating postures and compensatory methods. In recent years, fiber endoscopy has developed rapidly. FEES has been widely used to evaluate the swallowing function of patients, especially those after head and neck tumor surgery. FEES can directly observe the secretion of the pharynx and can intuitively obtain the swallowing process, such as anatomy, pharyngeal activity, and sensory disturbances. This study showed that the FEES test was similar to the diagnostic results of the Fibre Endoscopy Swallowing Function Assessment. It shows that using fiberoptic endoscopy to evaluate the swallowing function of patients is reliable and safe. At the same time, the method shows a high degree of specificity and sensitivity, which can be applied to clinical dietary management and swallowing function rehabilitation guidance for patients with dysphagia. .

Swallowing function recovery is a prerequisite for rapid postoperative rehabilitation of SCPL patients. In this study, early postoperative functional exercise promoted the recovery of swallowing function, which allowed patients to remove nasal feeding earlier, creating conditions for patients to recover quickly after surgery and reduce the average hospital stay.

In summary, fiberoptic endoscopic swallowing function test is a safe and reliable means to evaluate swallowing function, especially suitable for patients after SCPL operation. Early postoperative swallowing function training is useful for improving swallowing dysfunction in patients undergoing SCPL laryngeal cancer, Promoting the patient's rapid postoperative recovery and improving the patient's quality of life have certain effects. It is worth further exploring and improving effective training methods, and then forming a standardized training process for clinical application.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors report no conflict of interest. All authors were responsible for the content and writing of this paper.

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CONCLUSION

Fiber endoscopy is a reliable swallowing assessment method for patients' after SCPL, it is helpful to guide patients' diet management and rehabilitation treatment, and is worthy of clinical promotion and application.

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